

YULDOSH AKHUNBOBOEV MEMORIAL MUSEUM.

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Annotation: This article provides a detailed description of the organization, activities and exposition of the memorial museum of one of the statesmen and public figures, Yuldosh Akhunboboev, in Margilan, and a review of its closure.

Keywords: memorial, museum, state, public, politics, activities, exhibits, chairman, photographs, inventories, exhibition, historical documents.

Аннотация: Мазкур мақолада давлат ва жамоат арбобларидан бири Йўлдош Охунбобоевнинг Марғилонда фаолият юритган мемориал музейининг ташкил этилиши, музей фаолияти ҳамда экспозицияси шарҳи, тугатилиш шарҳи ҳақида батафсил ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: мемориал, музей, давлат, жамоат, сиёсат, фаолият, экспонатлар, раис, фотосуратлар, инвентарлар, кўргазма, тарихий ҳужжатлар.

Аннотация: В данной статье подробно описана организация мемориального музея Йулдоша Охунбобоева, одного из государственных и общественных деятелей, работавшего в Маргилоне, сделан обзор деятельности и экспозиции музея, а также обзор его прекращения.

Ключевые слова: мемориал, музей, государство, общественность, политика, деятельность, экспонаты, председатель, фотографии, описи, выставки, исторические документы.

Statesman and public figure Yuldosh Akhunboboev (1885-1943) was born in 1885 into a poor family in the village of Eski Joybazar, Yazyavan volost, Margilan uyezd, Ferhgana region. He began his career as a worker at a cotton ginning factory in Margilan (1901-1904), a hired farmer in Uzbek (1904-1914), chairman of the “Kushchi” union in Margilan (1919-1921), chairman of the Central Executive Committee of the Uzbek SSR (1925-1938), and chairman of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR (1938-1943).[1]

In order to perpetuate the memory of Yuldosh Akhunboboev and to commemorate the 40th anniversary of the formation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Yuldosh Akhunboboev Memorial Museum was established in the city of Margilan by the resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR dated October 17, 1964 “On the establishment of the Yuldosh Akhunboboev Memorial Museum in the city of Margilan”.[2]

The three-story museum building, built in 1974, is a worthy tribute to the services of the national elder to the people and the party, and a high symbol of the respect of the people and the country for him.[3] On June 30, 1975, on the occasion of the 90th anniversary of the birth of Yuldosh Akhunboboev, the museum building was put into operation.[4]

Until 1979, the museum operated as a branch of the Oybek museum of the history of the peoples of Uzbekistan, and since 1979, as a branch of the Fergana Regional Museum of Regional Studies. [5]

The total number of exhibits in the Yuldosh Akhunboboev Architectural Museum was 4016, of which 750 were placed in the museum halls for exhibition. [6]

According to the project, the total land area occupied by Yuldosh Akhunboboev memorial museum is set at 0.7. Usable land area is 560 square meters. Yuldosh Akhunboboev museum has a 114 sq.m. area, a 99-seat movie theater and a total of 587 sq.m. There are 6 exhibition halls with square.[7]

They are equipped to cover the following topics:

1.Hall. "Old Margilan", this hall displays household items, photographs, inventory, and tools that reflect the lifestyle of the people who lived in Margilan until the beginning of the 20th century.[8]

2-Hall. "Craftsmanship in Ancient Margilan", this hall displays exhibits showing that Margilan was an ancient silk-weaving and weaving town, as well as items made by craftsmen at that time, such as national clothes, scarves, and suzanas, and photographs.[9]

3.Hall. "The life and work of Yuldosh Akhunboboev from 1885 to 1939". This hall, which is aimed at highlighting the topic, uses more photographs reflecting the life of Yuldosh Akhunboboev than other halls. Also on display in this hall are Yuldosh Akhunboboev's personal belongings, gifts given to him, and original furniture and items from the interior of his office.[10]

4. Hall. "Yuldosh Akhunboboev activities on the eve of the war and during the war years" This hall displays photographs and historical documents depicting the activities of Yuldosh Akhunboboev on the eve of World War II, as well as photographs depicting Yuldosh Akhunboboev's departure to the Western Front during the war years, examples of daggers that belonged to him and were presented to the fighters by him, as well as photographs of Margilan veterans who fought heroically in World War II, orders and medals they received. Exhibition hall 5 is located in the upper part of the museum and shows his

creative work in the development of irrigation facilities in Uzbekistan with photographs, drawings and documents. [11]

6.Hall. Exhibition is mainly dedicated to displaying samples of products currently produced in Margilan, and to illustrating the life of Margilan during the years of independence.

In conclusion, it should be said that when the museum was first established, there was a large flow of visitors. Later, due to the lack of renewal of the expositions and neglect, the museum's activities remained in a cramped state. Later, in order to optimize the activities of museums, in 2006, the Akhunboboev's memorial museum was merged with the Margilan Museum of Art, which was then merged with the Margilan city history museum.

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